

Vibrational Sum Frequency Generation (VSFG) Spectroscopy of Electrocatalytic Mechanisms

Contact paul.donaldson@stfc.ac.uk, acowan@liverpool.ac.uk

G. Neri

Department of Chemistry and Stephenson Institute for Renewable Energy,
University of Liverpool, UK

P. M. Donaldson

Central Laser Facility, Research Complex at Harwell, STFC
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, UK

Introduction

Molecular electrocatalysts are being intensely studied for a range of reactions including the reduction of CO₂, O₂, H⁺ and the oxidation of water, amongst many others.^{1,2} The ability to synthetically modify molecular electrocatalysts, which are often small transition metal complexes, is of great benefit. However in order to enable rational catalyst modification it is important to be able to elucidate the catalytic mechanisms that occur with current state-of-the-art complexes.

A particular challenge is to be able to study the transient species that are present at an electrode surface during molecular electrocatalysis. Important catalytic intermediates may only be present at low concentrations at the electrode surface and traditional spectroscopic techniques can struggle to generate to differentiate between the bulk, inactive, catalyst and the desired intermediate.³ Vibrational sum frequency generation (VSFG) spectroscopy is a powerful interface selective technique that has been widely used to study surface catalytic processes in-situ.⁴⁻⁶ The theory of VSFG spectroscopy has been reported elsewhere.⁷ Briefly, VSFG is a 2nd order non-linear optical effect that can occur when two incident (IR and Visible) short laser pulses are overlapped spatially and temporally on a sample leading to the generation of light at the sum of the frequency of the incident IR and visible pulses. When the frequency of the IR light matches that of a vibrational mode a large increase in the intensity of the sum-frequency light occurs. The key property of VSFG is that for a vibrational mode to be sum frequency active it must be in both a macroscopic, and a molecular level, asymmetric environment, giving rise to the selectivity towards interfacial molecules.

Here we report some highlights of our recent activities examining the electrocatalytic mechanism using the ULTRA B experiment. Although VSFG has been used extensively to study a range of electro- active interfaces including for heterogeneous electrocatalysis, it has been rarely used to study homogenous electrocatalysts.^{4,8,9} Very recently we showed that at certain potentials solution molecular electrocatalysts exist either on, or within the electrode double layer (EDL) with sufficient ordering at certain applied potentials to enable detection by VSFG.¹⁰ We now examine the chemistry of one of the most widely studied electrocatalysts [Mn(bpy)(CO)₃(CH₃CN)]⁺ at an electrode surface in acetonitrile.^{11,12}

Scheme 1: Possible mechanism for electrocatalytic H₂ formation using [Mn(bpy)(CO)₃(CH₃CN)]⁺

A. J. Cowan

Department of Chemistry and Stephenson Institute for Renewable Energy,
University of Liverpool, UK

[Mn(bpy)(CO)₃(CH₃CN)]⁺ is a very selective catalyst for the reduction of CO₂ into CO (CO₂ + 2 e⁻ + 2H⁺ → CO + H₂O) and remarkably no significant H₂ evolution (2H⁺ + 2e⁻ → H₂), a thermodynamically less demanding process, is detected under a CO₂ atmosphere.¹¹ Here we do not study the interaction with CO₂ but instead explore this competitive mechanism of H₂ production with the aim of learning why the catalyst is selective to a single product. More generally the report outlines the capability of the CLF VSFG experiment to detect electrochemically generated intermediates at the electrode surface.

Experimental

VSFG spectra were recorded using the ULTRA B system. Full experimental details are covered elsewhere.¹³ Briefly 5 W of the output of a 20 W, 10 kHz, 50 fs, 800 nm Ti:Sapphire amplifier system (Coherent) is used to pump a OPA with two BBO and a AgGaS₂ DFG stage (CLF home build). The output of the OPA, a tunable IR source of ca. 500 cm⁻¹ usable bandwidth was focused onto the electrode surface (ca. 200 μm spot diameter, 1-4 μJ pulse) and overlapped spatially with a femtosecond derived picosecond 800 nm beam (ca. 300 μm spot diameter, 0.3-1.2 μJ pulse). The narrow-band femtosecond derived 800 nm beam is generated by passing 5 W of the amplified 800 nm through two air-spaced étalons (SLS optics, 21 and 9.5 cm⁻¹ transmission) which is passed through band-pass filter. At metal electrode surfaces large non-resonant SFG responses can be generated which mask the resonant VSFG spectrum. To suppress the non-resonant signal a short time delay (0.75 ps) was introduced between the IR and visible pulses.¹⁴ Generated VSFG signals were imaged with a 3 cm PCX lens, passed through a short pass filter (<750 nm, Semrock) and focused into a spectrograph (Holospec) and detected using a CCD array (Andor, Idus).

Figure 1: Schematic of the ULTRA-B VSFG experiment for the study of electrochemical interfaces.

The spectroelectrochemical cell is described elsewhere¹³ and consists of a teflon cross piece, CaF₂ front window, behind which the working electrode (50 μm pathlength) sits. The working electrode is a Hg-Au amalgam which is lightly polished by hand to improve reflectivity. A Pt counter and Ag pseudo reference electrode are present within the spectroelectrochemical cell.

Experiments are carried out on 1 mM $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{Br})]$ solutions using CH_3CN (anhydrous 99.8%) and 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium trifluorophosphate (TBAPF₆, $\geq 99.0\%$) as the supporting electrolyte. The potential of the working electrode with respect to the pseudo reference was controlled using a portable potentiostat (PalmSens 1). All solutions were thoroughly purged with Ar prior to transfer to the Ar purged spectroelectrochemical cell.

Results

The VSFG spectra of a 1 mM solution of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{Br})]$ in CH_3CN in the presence of 0.1 M TBAPF₆ during a cyclic voltammogram from +0.1 to -1.9 V_{Ag} recorded at 10 mV s⁻¹ are shown in figure 2. Initially only very weak VSFG features are present at $\sim 2045\text{ cm}^{-1}$ between +0.1 and -0.7 V_{Ag}. 2045 cm^{-1} is in good agreement with a $\nu(\text{CO})$ mode of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^+$.¹¹ We expect a mixture of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{Br}]$ and $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^+$ to be present as in Br⁻ exchanges with the solvent over the course of an experiment. Between -0.7 and -1.3 V_{Ag} a strong new ν_{CO} band can be seen to form at approximately 1970 cm^{-1} and it shifts in wavenumber with applied potential. The presence of such a Stark shift indicates that the vibrational mode is at, or very close to the electrode surface, confirming that our VSFG experiment is interrogating the correct interface.¹⁵ Furthermore all spectra are recorded with 1 s averaging highlighting the sensitivity of the Ultra VSFG experiment.

Figure 2: VSFG spectra recorded of the $\nu(\text{CO})$ region during CV of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{Br}]$ in CH_3CN TBAPF₆ (0.1 M) under Ar.

The band at approximately 1970 cm^{-1} first appears at the potential where the reduction of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^+$ occurs. It is known that reduction of two equivalents of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^+$ leads to the formation of a dimer $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$ and the VSFG band is assigned to this species on the basis of the known FTIR spectrum in solution ($\nu(\text{CO}) = 1973, 1927, 1880, 1849\text{ cm}^{-1}$).¹⁶ It is interesting to note that at the Au-Hg electrode that the 1973 cm^{-1} band is strongest between -0.7 and -1.2 V_{Ag}. We measure that peak current for reduction of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$ occurs at -1.25 V_{Ag}, at approximately the potential where the strong VSFG band assigned to this species decreases in intensity.

FTIR studies during the bulk electrolysis of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$ show the formation of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$, which in solution has $\nu(\text{CO})$ modes at 1911 and 1811 cm^{-1} .^{11,17} Careful inspection of the VSFG spectra in figure 2 recorded during between -1.25 to -1.90 V_{Ag} and between -1.90 back to -1.40 V_{Ag} shows the presence of a number of weaker VSFG bands. The relevant VSFG spectra are shown in figure 3. Multi-Lorentzian fitting of the spectra recorded at -1.35 V (figure 3(i)) shows the presence of a minimum of 3 bands, centered at $1966 (\pm 3), 1903 (\pm 2)$ and $1877 (\pm 3)\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at 1903 cm^{-1} may be related to

$[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ however on the basis of the known FTIR spectrum¹⁶ and observed potential dependence (see below) it appears likely that the VSFG spectra is instead of a small quantity of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$ remaining at the surface. In contrast to the VSFG spectra recorded between -0.7 to -1.2 V_{Ag} we now see more than one $\nu(\text{CO})$ band (at least 3 or the 4 possible) and with our current spectral resolution (*ca.* 15 cm^{-1}) we cannot rule out the presence of other overlapped VSFG bands, particularly between 1930 to 1850 cm^{-1} . Therefore it seems likely that a reorientation of the molecule at the electrode surface occurs between -0.7 to -1.2 V_{Ag} and -1.35 V_{Ag}.

Figure 3: Single VSFG spectra from the experiment shown in figure 2 at (i) -1.35 V_{Ag}, (ii) -1.60 V_{Ag}, (iii) and -1.50 V_{Ag}. Multi-Lorentzian fits are shown in green with the individual bands shown in red. Dashed lines link proposed assignments. The shifts in wavenumber between (i-iii) of bands assigned to the same species is likely to be due to vibrational Stark shifting.

By -1.60 V_{Ag} (figure 3(ii)) 2 new bands are present ($1994 (\pm 2), 1902 (\pm 2)\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the bands at $1966, 1903$ and 1877 almost completely gone, with only a weak band at $1964 (\pm 6)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ remaining from $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$. The bands at 1994 and 1902 cm^{-1} can not be assigned to $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$, instead they show good agreement with the FTIR spectrum of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$.¹⁶ As the potential is swept positive again we observe a decrease in the intensity of the VSFG bands of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$ and a recovery of the dimer complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]_2$, figure 3(iii).

The observation of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$ but not $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ in CH_3CN without an intentionally added Brønsted acid is an interesting result. VSFG spectra were recorded using anhydrous grade CH_3CN . It is apparent therefore that $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ is able to react even with trace levels of protons, available either directly from the CH_3CN itself or most likely from trace levels of water introduced when the spectroelectrochemical cell, which is not completely gas tight, is prepared or from incorrectly dried TBAPF₆. The observed facile formation of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$ and lack of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ at the electrode surface contradicts past spectroelectrochemical FTIR studies where $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ is found to form and be stable in the bulk solution under similar conditions.¹⁸ It is likely that in these past works where potentials are held for prolonged periods (minutes) the limited concentration of available protons was readily consumed. In contrast here we directly observe the transiently present concentration of the hydride complex at the electrode surface.

This result is significant as H_2 evolution would be expected to proceed *via* the formation of a hydride complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$ (scheme 1). One reason for the low levels of H_2 evolution during CO_2 reduction may have been due to a low

affinity of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ to H^+ . Clearly the observation of a VSFG spectra of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$ even in a solvent without a deliberately added acid shows that this is not the case and that the Mn hydride complexes are readily formed. Experiments under CO_2 to explore the binding constant of CO_2 ($K_{\text{CO}_2/\text{H}^+}$) to $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3]^-$ will be reported on shortly.

Conclusions

VSFG spectroscopy is shown to be a powerful tool to study interfacial electrochemistry using molecular electrocatalysts. Here we report on the behavior of $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{Br}]$ under Ar in the absence of a deliberately added acid to explore potential pathways to H_2 production. Interestingly, VSFG spectroscopy shows that formation of the hydride complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{H}]$, an intermediate during H_2 production is readily produced even in the presence of only very low concentrations of protons.

Acknowledgements

These experiments were carried out at the UK Central Laser Facility using UltraB (16.130.016 and 16.230.052) and were supported by the EPSRC (EP/K006851/1, EP/P034497/1).

References

- 1 S. Dey, B. Mondal, S. Chatterjee, A. Rana, S. Amanullah and A. Dey, *Nat. Rev. Chem.*, 2017, **1**, 98.
- 2 J.-M. Saveant, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 2348–2378.
- 3 K. J. Lee, N. Elgrishi, B. Kandemir and J. L. Dempsey, *Nat. Rev. Chem.*, 2017, **1**, 39.
- 4 N. G. Rey and D. D. Dlott, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2017, **800**, 114–125.
- 5 A. G. Lambert, P. B. Davies and D. J. Neivandt, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.*, 2005, **40**, 103–145.
- 6 S. Baldelli, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2005, **109**, 13049–13051.
- 7 Y. R. Shen, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2012, **116**, 15505–15509.
- 8 B. Braunschweig, P. Mukherjee, J. L. Haan and D. D. Dlott, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, , DOI:10.1016/j.jelechem.2016.10.035.
- 9 B. A. Rosen, J. L. Haan, P. Mukherjee, B. Braunschweig, W. Zhu, A. Salehi-Khojin, D. D. Dlott and R. I. Masel, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2012, **116**, 15307–15312.
- 10 G. Neri, P. M. Donaldson and A. J. Cowan, .
- 11 M. Bourrez, F. Molton, S. Chardon-Noblat and A. Deronzier, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2011, **50**, 9903–9906.
- 12 M. Stanbury, J.-D. Compain and S. Chardon-Noblat, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2018, **361**, 120–137.
- 13 G. Neri, P. M. Donaldson and A. J. Cowan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2017, **139**, 13791–13797.
- 14 A. Lagutchev, A. Lozano, P. Mukherjee, S. A. Hambir and D. D. Dlott, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 2010, **75**, 1289–1296.
- 15 D. M. Bishop, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 3179–3184.
- 16 F. Franco, C. Cometto, L. Nencini, C. Barolo, F. Sordello, C. Minero, J. Fiedler, M. Robert, R. Gobetto and C. Nervi, *Chem. - A Eur. J.*, 2017, **23**, 4782–4793.
- 17 K. A. Grice and C. P. Kubiak, in *CO2 Chemistry*, eds. M. Aresta and R. V Eldik, Elsevier Academic Press Inc, San Diego, 2014, vol. 66, pp. 163–188.